

Undiagnosed Type B Aortic Dissection in Pregnancy: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Aortic dissection during pregnancy is a life-threatening emergency for both mother and fetus; fortunately, it is a rare condition. This article presents the case of a 40-year-old patient diagnosed with preeclampsia without severe symptoms who, during the postpartum period, presented with persistent chest pain. During her evaluation, a computed tomography angiography (CTA) was performed, which revealed a type B aortic dissection (Stanford B, DeBakey III). The initial management consisted of conservative measures aimed at maintaining target blood pressure levels in a secondary-level hospital that lacks the infrastructure for multidisciplinary care. Therefore, referral to a tertiary care center was sought. This case clearly illustrates the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in resource-limited hospitals, highlighting the lack of specific protocols, multidisciplinary medical teams, and rapid inter-institutional referral networks.

KEYWORDS: Aortic dissection, Pregnancy, Acute aortic syndrome, Obstetrics emergency, Delayed diagnosis.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Aortic dissection during pregnancy is a rare but highly lethal medical emergency. It presents a considerable diagnostic challenge due to its nonspecific symptoms and overlap with common pregnancy discomforts. It is estimated to occur in fewer than 0.5 cases per 100,000 pregnancies. Its rapid and fulminant progression demands immediate identification and management to reduce the high associated maternal and fetal mortality.

Diagnosis is common during the third trimester of pregnancy and even in the early postpartum period, strongly associated with the physiological hemodynamic changes characteristic of this stage.

Timely diagnosis of this condition requires a high index of clinical suspicion, especially in women presenting with sudden onset of severe chest, back, or abdominal pain, with or without known risk factors. It should be noted that in

hospitals with limited advanced imaging resources, timely diagnosis is compromised.

Deficient inter-hospital networks lacking the capacity to resolve cases, which contributes to diagnostic delays, suboptimal decision-making and fatal outcomes, further compound this.

This article presents the case of an obstetric patient with Stanford type B aortic dissection, initially treated at a secondary-level hospital lacking the capacity to resolve cases. The absence of referral protocols and timely diagnosis resulted in fragmented management. This case highlights the urgent need to establish critical inter-institutional pathways, provide specific training for medical personnel on cardiovascular warning signs in pregnancy, and create effective referral and counter-referral networks that allow for comprehensive, coordinated, and appropriate care in these complex clinical scenarios.

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II. CLINICAL CASE

A 40-year-old woman, originally from the state of Yucatán and residing in Quintana Roo, was evaluated. She was married, Catholic, had completed high school education, and was a homemaker. With non-contributory Family history. Denied tobacco, alcohol, or illicit drug use; blood group and Rh factor O positive, history of scoliosis; known allergy to metamizole sodium; no chronic-degenerative diseases; no previous surgical or transfusional history. Menarche at 17 years of age; regular menstrual cycles every 30 days with moderate flow lasting 5 days; onset of sexual activity at 39 years of age; one lifetime sexual partner; denied having undergone prior cervical cytology screening. Gravida 1. Last menstrual period dated July 21, 2024. She attended three prenatal care visits with no documented complications; however, prenatal follow-up was considered inadequate. No obstetric ultrasound reports were available during prenatal care.

In March 2025, she presented to the obstetric emergency department of the Hospital General Jesús Kumate Rodríguez in Cancún after referral from a primary care facility with a presumptive diagnosis of spontaneous pneumothorax and a pregnancy of 34.1 weeks of gestation by last menstrual period. She reported a 12-hour history of sudden-onset precordial chest pain associated with dyspnea on moderate exertion. Upon admission, she was conscious, alert, cooperative, oriented to time, place, and person, with a Glasgow Coma Scale score of 15. She was hemodynamically stable. Vital signs at admission were as follows: blood pressure 108/66 mmHg, heart rate 74 beats per minute, respiratory rate 20 breaths per minute, temperature 36°C, oxygen saturation 99% on room air, weight 63 kg, and height 151 cm. Chest examination revealed no abnormalities, with preserved vesicular breath sounds and no added cardiac sounds. Abdominal examination showed a gravid uterus with a fundal height of 29 cm, present fetal movements, no uterine contractions during evaluation, fetal heart rate of 139 beats per minute, and no cervical changes.

Upon admission to the obstetric unit, an electrocardiogram, cardiac enzyme panel, chest radiograph (Figure 1), and cardiology consultation were requested. Cardiac enzymes were within normal limits. The electrocardiogram showed chamber dilation without other significant findings. Chest radiography revealed dilation of the aortic arch, initially suggesting valvular or vascular pathology. The cardiology service recommended computed tomography angiography for further diagnostic evaluation; however, this study could not be performed at admission due to lack of necessary supplies.

The patient remained hospitalized under diagnostic evaluation. On hospital day four, she was classified as preeclampsia without severe features based on elevated blood pressure values with a normal preeclampsia laboratory profile. A decision was made to terminate the pregnancy via

caesarean section. The surgical procedure was uneventful. A male newborn was delivered, weighing 2,820 g and measuring 44 cm in length, with Apgar scores of 7 and 7 at one and five minutes, respectively. Gestational age by the Capurro method was 36 weeks. The umbilical cord was three-vessel, and placental delivery was unremarkable. Estimated blood loss was 300 mL.

The newborn was transferred to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, where he showed favorable evolution and was subsequently discharged. At the conclusion of surgery, the patient was transferred to the Intensive Care Unit for monitoring. During the immediate postpartum period, she developed elevated blood pressure values with difficult control and persistent, transfixing chest pain. Computed tomography angiography was performed, identifying a Stanford type B, DeBakey type III aortic dissection (figures 2-4).

Following this diagnosis, the patient was managed with multiple antihypertensive agents by the cardiology service to maintain target blood pressure levels. Cardiothoracic surgery evaluated the patient and determined that she was a candidate for endovascular exclusion of the thoracic and visceral aortic segments. Consequently, transfer to a tertiary care center for definitive management was requested, as the secondary-level hospital lacked the necessary human and material resources to perform endovascular or surgical intervention. A referral protocol to a tertiary-level medical center with cardiovascular capabilities was initiated.

After 29 days of hospitalization, the patient requested voluntary discharge, stating that she had health coverage through the Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social (IMSS). The subsequent clinical outcome is unknown.

Figure 1. AP chest x-ray with evidence of aortic knob dilation and scoliosis.

Figure 2. Coronal reconstruction of chest and abdominal CT angiography with IV contrast showing intimamedial flap in thoracic aorta with double lumen (true and false lumen), consistent with Stanford type B / DeBakey type III aortic dissection, with extension to abdominal aorta.

Figure 3. Coronal reconstruction of chest CT angiography with IV contrast showing intimamedial flap in ascending aorta and aortic arch, with double lumen, corresponding to Stanford type B aortic dissection.

Figure 4. Intimamedial flap in descending thoracic aorta, consistent with distal extension of type B (Stanford) aortic dissection.

III. DISCUSSION

Aortic dissection associated with pregnancy and the postpartum period is an uncommon condition but with high maternal and fetal mortality. Timely diagnosis is often hampered by the nonspecific clinical presentation and limitations in appropriate diagnostic tools. This case illustrates the importance of investigating nonspecific symptoms such as chest pain. In this patient, the dilation of the aortic arch, coupled with pain, were the pivotal symptoms that pointed to a vascular pathology. It should be noted that the lack of immediate access to CT angiography led to a delay in diagnosis. The preeclampsia, without signs of severity, diagnosed during the hospital stay, most likely contributed to the hemodynamic deterioration and progression of the aortic dissection, a situation that has been described in patients without evidence of prior connective tissue diseases. Furthermore, the confirmation of aortic dissection during the postpartum period is consistent with the literature, which identifies this period as one of increased risk for developing this condition. According to international guidelines, this condition can initially be managed conservatively; however, in this patient, the cardiothoracic surgery evaluation determined that she was a candidate for endovascular surgical management. The inability to offer comprehensive and definitive management at the medical unit and the absence of effective referral protocols necessitated the timely transfer to a center with the capacity to resolve the issue.

This case highlights the diagnostic and therapeutic limitations in resource-constrained settings and underscores the need to strengthen clinical suspicion, ensure timely access to advanced imaging studies, and implement rapid referral networks for obstetric cardiovascular emergencies. The lack of follow-up, resulting from voluntary discharge, is a limitation of this report, but it underscores the vulnerability of these patients when established critical care pathways are lacking.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Aortic dissection in obstetric patients is a rare condition; however, its high mortality rate necessitates considering serious vascular pathologies in cases of nonspecific symptoms, such as persistent chest pain. This case highlights the impact of delayed diagnosis and referral to specialized centers, resulting from the lack of effective referral and counter-referral protocols, as well as infrastructure limitations in secondary care hospitals.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This case report has been removed from all data related to the patient.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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